

Tracking the Presence of Classics in Early Modern England: the first steps of PreCEM

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The impact of Classics on Early Modern cultural production is well known (see for instance Enenkel 2013), but precious little has been done to provide quantitative information related to the topic. With this paper, we aim to introduce the first stages of the PreCEM (Presence of Classics in Early Modern Book History) project joining Helsinki, KU Leuven, and Aalto expertise to improve the detection of classical authors' presence in texts and metadata sets of Early Modern works. More precisely, the project focuses on the exploitation of the broad collections of printed (meta)data for British books (1470–1800) available in machine-readable form: Eighteenth Century Collections Online (ECCO) and Early English Books Online (EEBO-tcp phase II). The Helsinki Computational History Group (COMHIS) has developed significant expertise both in the exploitation of the metadata (cf. Tolonen et al. 2022 on the features of ECCO, and forthcoming work on EEBO) and in the study of text reuse within the OCRed texts available in the two collections (cf. Salmi et al. 2020 on a similar experiment). In this presentation, we will first introduce the strategies applied to identify the publications of classical authors in the two datasets, and subsequently provide a first overview of the results (building on Tolonen et al. 2019). In the conclusion, we will briefly sketch the forthcoming work on text-reuse detection and its specific challenges. By looking both at metadata and text reuse we want to assess, for instance, how Cicero's works are disseminated and how cultural constituents transform when they travel through centuries of editions, quotes, and allusions.

The ECCO catalogue currently includes metadata of about 480,000 documents published between 1473 and 1800, whereas the EEBO catalogue includes ca 135,000 records. Amongst the information available in the metadata are language, publication date, length of the work. Both datasets are mapped to the ESTC (English Short Title Catalogue), with e.g. additional biographical data, and to the EEBO-TCP (Text Creation Partnership), with transcriptions for a subset of the EEBO texts. Metadata are partially standardised, e.g. languages and language types are recorded following MARC standards, and the IDs of the authors are mapped to [VIAF](#) identifiers.

Given the size of the EEBO and ECCO datasets, manually selecting records that contain publications of classical authors would be a cumbersome task. For this reason, we test different approaches to filter them, and assess the results of the approaches.

Part I: retrieving classical works

A first, naïve, approach starts from the biographical information available in the ESTC authors database: dates of birth, death, or first publication, pulled from various sources including VIAF. We retrieve Latin and Ancient Greek ESTC authors for which at least one

recorded date is prior to the 6th century (taken as the symbolic end of Late Antiquity). The resulting list, manually checked, contains 294 out of the 127,066 records (0.2%). A second approach consists in relying on existing authority lists. For the classical world, [Trismegistos Authors](#) (TM Authors) provides a comprehensive list of the authors known from 800 BC up to AD 800. The list contains 7331 ancient authors, of which 2387 mapped to VIAF identifiers. Since also the ESTC authors have been mapped to VIAF identifiers, by merging the two lists, we expect to retrieve the classical authors present in the ESTC authors list. However, the number of authors retrieved in this way is surprisingly lower (258) than the list retrieved with the previous method. An investigation of the difference between the two sets reveals that the problems mostly stem from i) the existence of multiple VIAF IDs for the same person, ii) the absence of VIAF identifier either in ESTC or Trismegistos, iii) the absence of an author in TM Authors, mostly because of a different conception of the notion of author (e.g. Jesus Christ is considered an author in ESTC, but not in Trismegistos), and iv) the more extended time-span of TM Authors (up to the 8th century). The comparison between the two lists shows the danger of relying exclusively on shared identifiers (even when they are supposed to be stable): among others, the works of Livy, Pindar and Seneca would have been missed. A final comprehensive list of 312 ESTC classical authors up to the 6th century is used as a starting basis for retrieving classical works in the EEBO and ECCO datasets. The results are shown in Table 1:

Database	Works by Classical Authors	Total	Rate
ESTC	6307	485578	1,2%
EEBO	2036	112131	1,8%
EEBO (no TCP)	1474	54674	2,6%
EEBO-TCP	562	57457	1%
ECCO	2550	184327	1,4%

Table 1: Classical works in EEBO and ECCO

Part II: Printing of classics across time.

The second part of the talk will provide a few results based on the statistical exploitation of the data. In particular we will discuss:

1. The representativity of ECCO and EEBO (esp. EEBO-TCP) for studying the publication of classics
2. The diachronic evolution of the printing of classics across the Early Modern period
3. The distribution of language, to answer the question of what were the most important languages in which the classical heritage was accessed

We will conclude with an overview of the most frequently published authors and the distribution of works per author in EEBO and ECCO, which provides an indication of the evolution of the canon in the targeted period.

Based on this data, we will outline the main challenges that we expect to face in the second part of the project, i.e. the study of text reuse of classical authors: the low representation of classics in the EEBO-TCP dataset, the varying performance of OCR on different scripts and the conceptual difficulty of defining text reuse in a cross-lingual context, and the conceptual problem of grounding the study of text reuse of classics to the reuse of segments of works that were being printed in Early Modern England.

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